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Assessment of Learning Curve Theory and Labour Performances in Maiduguri Flour Mill, Borno- Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

This paper attempted to test if the learning curve theory was not applicable to Maiduguri Flour Mills. The wide spread application of the learning curve theory has not been tested in Maiduguri Flour Mills. The methodology utilized the use of secondary sources of data from the company to test the applicability of the theory. The model $y = ax^b$ was used to assess the applicability of the learning curve theory in Maiduguri Flour Mills, Borno-Nigeria. The result showed that learning curve theory was applicable to this company with an indication of the unit variable cost decreasing from one level of doubled output to another. Therefore, the paper rejected the null hypothesis, and accepted that the theory of learning curve was applicable to this company. The study recommended that the labourers' effort should be motivated so that they can increase their skills and dexterity at work, so as to reap the full benefit of the theory.

Keywords: Learning curve theory, labour performances, Maiduguri Flour Mills and Borno-Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

The theory of learning curve can be traced to the work of Bills (1934), Bruce (1960) and Hartley (1965) which stated that when an inexperienced labour performs a repetitive work, the average labour hours falls by specific percentage when output doubles. The curve relates to labour's repeated efforts in performing the same job day in and day out. The curve is often represented in a graphical form to depict how average labour time drops as output doubles. The doubling of the output is achieved as a result of a worker gaining efficiency, skills and dexterity in the production process.

The theory has a wide application in aircraft and production companies. But no work has been done to assess its applicability in Maiduguri Flour Mills. The Borno Flour Mills have powerful machines that produce samovita, flour and dusa to the teeming population both within and outside Maiduguri. Labour efficiency and effectiveness is noted when learning effect has taken place. It appears that even the workers themselves do not understand the principle and application of the model $y = ax^b$.

The objective of this paper is to test the applicability of learning curve in Maiduguri, Nigeria. Another specific objective is to assess their production process whether it follows the pattern of learning curve theory.

The statement of hypothesis tested in this paper is: HO - Learning curve theory is not applicable to Maiduguri Flour Mills.

Literature review and conceptual framework

According to Adeniyi (2004), the origin of the learning curve theory was developed in 1920. ICAN study pact (2006) claimed that the theory was first developed in 1925, while others lend support to the work of Bill (1934). Controversy clouded the exact date the theory was first developed. The Wikipedia, free encyclopedia (2012) reported that the first person to describe the learning curve theory was Ebbinghaus in 1885. However, their conceptual definitions cut across the fact that average labour hours falls by specific percentage as output doubles. When average time hours taken to perform a task drops, such a worker should be motivated through incentive plans.

Omolehinwa (2002) subscribed to the fact that repetitive performance of a task reduces the unit variable cost. When a labour has mastered the operations of a task, it takes a shorter time frame to complete a production work. Operations of work by inexperienced workers do not lend support to the learning curve theory, rather, it is when there is repetition of task, a stable labour force, and a consistent job done with no case of workers quitting. Learning task operations and logic requires careful training and practice in order to achieve a doubled output. Abilla (2007)

described learning curve to be a graphical representation of the changing rate of learning for a given activity or tool. The curve at a glance showed the initial difficulties of learning something and how much there is to learn after initial familiarity. The concept stated that there is less and less learning as more repetitive steps are taken. The conditions that must exist before learning curve takes place are: stable labour force, repetitive task and continuity of job.

Consistency in improvement has been found to exist in the form of a constant reduction in time required over successively doubled quantities of units produced (Abilla, 2007). The slope of the curve is measured as hundred (100) minus the rate of learning. Zangwill and Kantor (1998) observed that continuous improvement unceasingly strives to improve the performance of production and service firms. The learning curve provides a means to observe and track that improvement.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptually, the learning curve theory was referred to as experience curve, improvement curve, cost improvement, progress curve and efficiency curve (Ebbinghaus, 1885). The theoretical framework adopted in this paper is the one theorised by Abilla (2007) which stated that when continuous learning takes place, labour output doubles. Most theorist have a similar concept, but Abilla (2007) is most appropriate in this paper.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this paper is experimental method. Production and labour records of the Flour Mill were extracted. Respondents were asked face-to-face questions on learning curve theory to establish applicability in this company. The questions centered on the budgeted initial output level and labour hours. Based on that, one can draw the idea of the theory and see whether it's applicable to this company.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Records of Maiduguri Flour Mills have been inspected. Information regarding initial hours required to produce the first batch of output together with cost of materials, labour rate and fixed cost of production was obtained from the costing department. Face to face interview on the concept of learning curve in the company did not hint on its applicability in the production department. All the workers in the production department said that their speed of operation have increased tremendously because they have been in this job for many years. Most of the workers interviewed did not even know what learning curve is or its applicability. Table 1 below contains information extracted from the company record.

Table 1: Budgeted input costs

Item	Amount (₦)
Material cost	2,500,000
Fixed cost	5,000,000
Labour charges	500/hour

Source: Fieldwork, 2012.

Table 2: Budgeted units and labour hours

Expected initial output	400 bags of samovita
Budgeted labour hours	3531 hours

Source: Fieldwork, 2012.

To test the applicability of learning curve, the paper has to remind the reader of the theoretical formula used in the theories that confirm the application of learning curve in production companies. The learning curve theory is expressed in the form of $y = ax^b$ where, y = average labour hour, a = initial hour taken to do the first units of output, x = represent cumulative units of output and b = index of learning curve.

To establish whether their production output followed learning curve theory, the formula $Y = a x^b$ was used in the analysis. This implies that $y = 3,531/1(400/1)^{\log_{.80}/\log 2}$. When this equation is simplified, it gives an answer of 5 1 2

hours. When output doubled, that is initial output of 400 doubled to 800 bags of samovita, the average labour hours now dropped to 410 hours. When output:

Output	average labour hours
400	512
800	410
1600	232

Cost per unit at 400 level off output

	N
Materials	2,500,000
Labour cost (N500 x512)	256,000
Fixed cost (N5, 000,000/400)	12,500
Total cost/unit	<u>N 2,768,500</u>

Cost per unit at 800 level of output

Material	2,500,000
Labour cost (N500 x 410)	205,000
Fixed cost (N5, 000,000/800)	6,250
Total cost/unit	<u>N 2,711,250</u>

Cost per unit at 1,600 units of output

Materials	2,500,000
Labour cost (N500 x232)	116,000
Fixed cost (N5, 000,000/1,600)	3,125
Total cost/unit	<u>N 2,619,125</u>

The decline in the total cost per unit from N2, 768,500 to N 2, 711,250 indicated the result of the effect of learning curve theory. The pictorial decline showed that:

Learning curve was applicable to Maiduguri Flour Mills. This implies that higher target output should be envisaged to achieve the full benefit of the effect of learning curve theory. The summary of findings is shown in the table 3 below:

Table 3: Summary of findings

Output	Average hours	Decrease in total cost(N)
400	512	2,768,500
800	410	2,711,250
1,600	232	2,619,125

Source: Fieldwork, 2012.

The decline in average labour hours and variable cost in table 3 as output doubles demonstrated that learning curve theory has taken place. Labour efficiency and effectiveness in Maiduguri Flour Mills revealed that the theory of learning curve is applicable in the company. The result clearly support the works of Bills (1934) and Bruce (1960) which infers that as experience and skills improves, the average labour hours drops at certain percentages. Hence, this paper rejects the hypothesis that learning curve is not applicable in Maiduguri Flour Mills, and accepts that the theory is applicable.

The fact that some workers that might not know that their efforts and skills followed the learning curve theory, will begin to seek for promotion, leave study and holidays as part of their contribution to the company. Once a cost center manger recommends a worker for a job well done, this implies that learning curve has taken place and the company should also reciprocate by remunerating labour effort. This will make the worker to put in more effort in the job.

CONCLUSION

The test of the applicability of learning curve theory has been conducted in Maiduguri Flour Mill. The result showed that the theory is applicable in this company with unit cost and labour hours decreasing as output level doubles. Companies that are labour intensive can devise means where by workers can find the job interesting and satisfying thereby resulting in output doubling and unit cost of production reducing proportionately.

RECOMMENDATION

The paper recommended that production companies should find more ways of motivating and encouraging their workers to double their efforts, skills and dexterity without being coerced.

COMPETING INTEREST

The environment in which Maiduguri Flour Mill operates is quite different from others. Likewise the capacity and quality of machines used could differ from one company to another. Quality of output, labour efficiency and dexterity could also vary from company to company. Learning curve theory often takes some labour longer time to master the job. Training skills may not be the same with another place. The author in this study declared that learning curve theory was applicable to Maiduguri Flour Mill, Borno –Nigeria despite the technological and technical know-how.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

The Author was able to establish that learning curve is universally applicable to companies that is labour intensive given technological know - how of the job.

REFERENCES

- Abilla P (2007). Learning curve theory, experience curve. www.shmula.com
- Adeniyi A (2004). An insight to Management Accounting, 3rd Edition Value Analysis publishers, Lagos.
- Bills AG (1934). General experimental psychology, Longmans psychology series, New York, Longmans, Green and co, pp192-215.
- Bruce H (1960). The experience curve and its implication for strategy.
- Zangwill WI and Kantor BP (1998). Toward a theory of continuous improvement and the learning curve. www.jstor.org/stable/2634506.
- Ebbinghaus H (1885). Learning curve in psychology and economics.
- Hartley K (1965). The learning curve and its application to the Aircraft Industry.
- ICAN study packs (2006). Management accounting professional Examination 11.
- Omolehinwa E (2002). Coping with cost accounting. Pumark, publishers, Agege Lagos, Nigeria.

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